

Configurational Interaction and Distribution of Defect Pairs In Ionic Solids*

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The distribution of $V'_X - V'_M$ and $I'_M - V'_M$ pairs in CsCl and CsCl-Sr²⁺ systems have been worked out using the association energies obtained from ionic lattice calculations for the first few bound states. Similar curves have also been drawn for KCl and KCl-Sr²⁺ systems with the recently reported values of association energies. The order of predominance of $Sr'_{Cs} - V'_{Cs}$ and $Sr'_{K} - V'_{K}$ pairs is $C_{3v}(111) > C_{4v}(200) > C_s(210) > C_{2v}(110) > C_{4v}(100)$ and $C_{4v}(200) > C_s(310) > C_{2v}(220) > C_{2v}(110) > C_s(211)$ respectively. In the case of $V'_{Cs} - V'_{Cl}$ and $V'_{K} - V'_{Cl}$ pairs we found the following order, $C_{3v}(\frac{1}{2}\frac{1}{2}\frac{1}{2}) > C_s(\frac{3}{2}\frac{1}{2}\frac{1}{2}) > C_s(\frac{3}{2}\frac{1}{2}\frac{1}{2})$ and $C_{4v}(100) > C_s(210) > C_{4v}(300) + C_s(211) > C_{3v}(111)$ respectively.

In alkali halides, we generally encounter intrinsic Schottky defects whose concentration is entirely defined by the temperature of the solid and extrinsic defects caused by the incorporation of divalent cation impurities. According to the law of mass action¹, both the cation-anion vacancy pairs (denoted by *vp* or $V'_M - V'_X$) and the divalent cation impurity-vacancy pairs (denoted by *ip* or $I'_M - V'_M$) remain either associated or dissociated throughout the lattice. Although, earlier workers²⁻⁴ assumed that the defect pairs are associated only at the nearest distance of approach, recent esr⁵⁻⁸ and Zeeman Fluorescence⁹ studies clearly indicate the importance of several first few associated states. A knowledge of the distribution of defect pairs in different associated states is necessary to find out which of the defect pairs are to be treated explicitly in the defect model used in the interpretation of ionic conductivity and diffusion in alkali halides. Presently, we have carried out an evaluation of the distribution of $I'_M - V'_M$ and $V'_X - V'_M$ pairs in both pure and Sr²⁺ doped CsCl and KCl systems as a function of temperature.

Distribution Functions : In deriving the distribution functions it is necessary to know the association energies of the defect pairs in several of the bound states; in the Coulombic approximation these energies are given by

$$E_j^{ip(vp)} = e^2/(\epsilon R_j) \quad \dots (1)$$

where R_j is the distance between the two defects in the associated state j and ϵ is the static dielectric constant of the solid. Ionic lattice calculations, however, predict energies lower

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than the Coulombic values at least for the first associated state pairs. This arises from the repulsive interaction due to electron overlap and the polarization of the lattice about the defect pair; similar reasoning also holds good for the next few associated states. Accurate estimations of the first few associated state energies have been carried out^{10,11} by means of ionic lattice calculations using the Mott-Littleton³ description of the displacement field. Association energies $E_j^{ap(i,p)}$ thus calculated (in eV) are as follows :

	$j = 1$	$j = 2$	$j = 3$	$j = 4$
CsCl-Sr ²⁺	0.21	0.31	0.70	0.42
KCl-Sr ²⁺	0.33	0.51	0.21	—
CsCl	0.41	0.30	—	—
KCl	0.69	0.35	0.36	—

Substituting these values of the association energies and applying the Coulombic approximation for higher associated states, we are in a position to obtain the distribution curves for the two systems.

The following assumptions have been made in deriving the distribution functions :

(i) only pair-wise interactions between defects in a given pair have been considered, (ii) the dipolar interaction between defect pairs are omitted, (iii) only the configurational part of the entropy term is included in the free energy expression; the vibrational part is considered to be independent of the arrangement of defects, and (iv) the concentration of the associated defects is much less than that of the isolated impurities and valencies. Thus, the number of ways of distributing m_j number of associated vacancy pairs of bound state j can be described by,

$$2^{m_j} L_j^{m_j} \prod_{s=0}^{s=m_j} \frac{\pi [N_+ + N_v^\pm - \sum_i' (m_i - s)]}{m_j !} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

Here, the summation with subscript i is carried over 30 bound states and the prime denotes the omission of terms when $i = j$; N_+ is the total number of cation sites, N_v is the total number of vacancies of one kind, the factor, 2^{m_j} takes care of the positive and negative ion vacancies; the factor m_j in the denominator represents the indistinguishability among the various vacancy pairs of a particular state j , L_j is the number of equivalent positions defined by the point group symmetry (see Appendix) of a given defect pair. Thus, the total number of configurations for the random mixing of m_j vacancy pairs formed by $N_{\pm v}$ cation and anion vacancies on N_+ and N_- available sites is given by,

$$\Omega_{(V_{\dot{X}} - V'_M)} = \left\{ \prod_{j=1}^{j=1} \frac{\pi [N_+ + N_v^\pm - \sum_i' (m_i - s)]}{m_j !} \right\} \\ \times \left\{ \frac{(2N_+ + 2N_v^\pm - 2\sum_i m_i) !}{N_+ ! N_- ! (N_{v^+} - \sum_i m_i) ! (N_{v^-} - \sum_i m_i) !} \right\} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

and the configurational entropy of association can be written as

$$S_a = k \ln \Omega \quad \dots (4)$$

Similarly for the divalent cation impurity-cation vacancy pairs we can write

$$\Omega_{(I_M-V'_M)} = \left\{ \prod_{j=1}^{j=i} \frac{\pi}{L_j} L_j^{n_j} \frac{\pi^{s=0} [N_+ + 2N_i - 2\sum'(n_i - 2s)]^{s=n_j}}{n_j!} \right\} \\ \times \left\{ \frac{(N_+ + 2N_i - 2\sum n_i)!}{N_+! (N_i - \sum_i n_i)! (N_i - \sum_i n_i)!} \right\} \quad \dots (5)$$

where N_i and n_j are the total number of impurity atoms and the number of associated complexes in the j -th state respectively.

For both the kinds of defect pairs, the free energy of association can be expressed by

$$F_a = \sum_j n_j E_j^{ip} - T S_a^{ip} \quad \text{or} \quad \sum_j m_j E_j^{vp} - T S_a^{vp} \quad \dots (6)$$

At equilibrium,

$$\sum_{j=1}^i n_j \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial n_j} \right) T, P, n_{i \neq j} = 0 \quad \dots (7)$$

Using the Stirling approximation and the assumptions mentioned earlier, we get

$$\frac{m_j N_+}{(N_v \pm \sum_i m_j)^2} = (L_j/2) \exp(E_j^{vp}/kT)$$

but

$$\sum_{j=1}^i (L_j/2) \exp(E_j^{vp}/kT) = \frac{N_v N_+}{(N_v \pm \sum m_j)^2} \quad \dots (8)$$

Thus,

$$\left(\frac{m_j}{N_v} \right) = \frac{L_j \exp(E_j^{vp}/kT)}{\sum L_j \exp(E_j^{vp}/kT)} \quad \dots (9)$$

represents the Boltzmann distribution function for the vacancy pairs. Similarly for the divalent cation impurity-vacancy pairs in the state j , we have

$$\left(\frac{n_j}{N_i} \right) = \frac{L_j' \exp(E_j^{ip}/kT)}{\sum L_j' \exp(E_j^{ip}/kT)} \quad \dots (10)$$

The summations in eqns. (9) and (10) were carried over 30 associated states after confirming the invariance of these quantities in the temperature range 100–800 K. The distribution curves thus obtained are shown in Figs. 1–4. In his analysis of the distribution of defect pairs in KCl-Sm²⁺ system, Fong¹ uses the Coulombic values from the second associated

Fig. 1. Distribution of intrinsic $V'Cl-V'K$ pairs obtained by assuming Coulombic values of association energies from the third bound state onwards. Here, $E_3^{vp}(\text{Theoretical}) = E_3^{vp}(\text{Coulombic})$

Fig. 2. Distribution of intrinsic $V'Cl-V'Cs$ pairs obtained by assuming Coulombic values of association energies from the second bound state onwards. Here, $E_2^{vp}(\text{Theoretical}) = E_2^{vp}(\text{Coulombic})$.

Fig. 3. Distribution of $I_K-V'_K$ pairs obtained by assuming Coulombic values of association energy after the third associated state.

state onwards; this does not appear to be correct (particularly for CsCl-Sr^{2+}) as can be seen from the values of the theoretical estimates of association energies listed earlier. The E_3^{ip} value in the case of KCl-Sr^{2+} system is also lower than the Coulombic value. In Fig. 5 we have plotted n_j/N_i for the CsCl-Sr^{2+} system assuming Coulombic values from the second associated state onwards in order to throw some light on the effect of association energies on the distribution curves.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the distribution curves of the intrinsic $V_{Cl}-V'_K$ pairs (Fig. 1), we find the predominance of the $C_{4v}(100)$ pair; a lesser probability of occurrence is found for the $C_s(210)$ and $C_{3v}(111)$ pairs. These results are in line with the calculated association energies. With Coulombic values, n_j/N_i would be reversed for $C_s(210)$ and $C_{3v}(111)$ pairs. Even in the CsCl system, the first associated state $C_{3v}(\frac{1}{2}\frac{1}{2}\frac{1}{2})$ pairs predominate over the others. There appears to be a qualitative difference in the shape of the distribution curves for the intrinsic defects in KCl and CsCl . While in KCl the $C_{4v}(100)$ pair predominate right upto 800 K (with increasing population of the other pairs only beyond this temperature), in CsCl we find significant concentration of both the first and second associated states upto 800 K.

Fig. 4. Distribution of $I'_{Cs} - V_{Cs}$ pairs obtained by assuming Coulombic value of association energy after the fourth associated state.

This suggests that the deviations, observed in using the Einstein relation for diffusion, must be attributed to movement of ions through first and second associated state pairs in CsCl while in KCl the usual procedure of considering only the first associated state pair may be correct.

More interesting features of the distribution phenomena are seen in the case of KCl-Sr²⁺ and CsCl-Sr²⁺ system (Figs. 3 and 4). In both these systems, the pairs whose configurations contain a special defect situation ($C_{4v}(200)$ in KCl-Sr²⁺ and $C_{3v}(111)$ in CsCl-Sr²⁺) with a collinear arrangement of $Sr_M - Cl - V'_M$ sites seems to dominate over the others. In the case of $Sr_K - V'_K$ pairs the predominance of $C_{4v}(200)$ is corroborated by studies of ESR⁵ and optical Zeeman Fluorescence spectra⁹. The signals attributed to the C_{2v} sites apparently arise from both (110) and (220) pairs of equal probability; this is in variation with the earlier suggestion¹ that next to $C_{4v}(200)$, $C_{2v}(110)$ pair predominates over the others. The present theory predicts nicely the absence of C_{3v} sites (as observed by Watkins⁵). Although, there are no experimental data to corroborate the present findings regarding $Sr_{Cs} - V'_{Cs}$ pairs, some preliminary ESR studies of CsBr-Mn²⁺ and CsCl-Mn²⁺ systems^{7,8} show the presence of $C_{4v}(100)$ pair; no signal corresponding to the $C_{2v}(110)$ pair seems to have been observed. These ESR investigations were, however, not designed to detect the $C_{3v}(111)$ pairs and the other monoclinic cation sites; further investigations are necessary to prove the validity of these findings from theory.

The present studies clearly show that we should be careful in choosing Coulombic values for the association energies of the lower associated states, since in these states the presence of short range forces would result in much lower values of the association energies. For example, in the CsCl-Sr²⁺ system, the distribution curves obtained by assuming Coulombic values for the association energies from the second bound state onwards show larger probability for the C_{2v}(110) pair (Fig. 5). ESR data⁷, however, show no such evidence. We may on the other hand, safely assume Coulombic values for the association energies in the case of higher bound state pairs because of the increasing distance between the two defects. In fact, this appears to be the only recourse since ionic lattice calculations are cumbersome and unreliable as we go to higher states.

Fig. 5. Distribution of $V-C_s$ pairs obtained by assuming the Coulombic values of association energy after the first associated state.

In view of the present results showing the importance of the first few associated state pairs, there appears to be need for reexamining the diffusion and ionic conductivity data in ionic solids. The defect model used in interpreting these experimental results should treat the first few important associated pairs explicitly; in the literature, only the first bound pair has been considered as a distinct defect while the rest of the interactions were treated

in terms of the Debye-Hückel theory. A further remark would be in order with respect to the distribution functions. Fong and coworkers^{13,14} have noted that at elevated temperatures the ion-defect pairs dissociate and the concept of pair formation more appropriately gives way to the concept of pair correlation functions. The grand partition function of the canonical configuration should contain the associative and dissociative interactions between intrinsic and extrinsic defects in the whole temperature range. Such configuration partition would be least susceptible to high defect concentrations; at low defect concentrations (at high temperature $N_i \ll N_v^\pm$), however, the canonical partition function reduces to the molecular function as shown above.

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APPENDIX

*Site Symmetries of the $I_M-V'_M$ and $V_X-V'_M$ Pairs in CsCl Lattice**

When an anion vacancy or a divalent cation impurity is located at the origin, the associated cation vacancies of the respective $V_X-V'_M$ and $I_M-V'_M$ pairs occupy discrete positions permitted by the lattice and the Coulombic values of association energies assume discrete values in accordance with eqn. (1). Taking the structural properties of the CsCl lattice into consideration, we find in the case of the first associated state of the $V_X-V'_M$ pairs, eight equivalent but distinguishable sites where the C_{3v} symmetry of the pair points in the directions of the $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})$ $(-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2})$ $(-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})$ $(-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2})$ $(\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2})$ $(\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})$ $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2})$ and $(-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})$ lattice points. For the first associated state of the $I_M-V'_M$ pair, we have the charge compensation on the simple cubic cation sub-lattice where the equivalent configurations are described by the C_{4v} symmetry pointing towards $(1, 0, 0)$, $(0, 1, 0)$, $(0, 0, 1)$, $(-1, 0, 0)$, $(0, -1, 0)$ and $(0, 0, -1)$ lattice points. With the anion vacancy (or the divalent cation impurity) at the origin, the cation vacancy at (l, m, n) will form a vacancy pair (or a divalent cation impurity-vacancy pair) depending on whether l, m , and n are half-integers (or integers). The distance between the two defects in a given pair is simply given by $(l^2+m^2+n^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}a_0$ where a_0 is the lattice constant. In the case of $V_X-V'_M$ pairs, R_j in eqn. (1) can assume values of $a_0\sqrt{(8j-5)/2}$, where $j = 1, 2, 3$ etc. while in the case of $I_M-V'_M$ pairs, the distance between the two defects is given in terms of $R_j = a_0\sqrt{j}$.

The distance, point group symmetry of the associated pair and its number of equivalent configuration (L_j) for states $j \leq 30$ are summarized in Tables 1 and 2. Some of the associated states are described by more than one site symmetry and since the association energies in these states have identical values, the distribution of defect pairs pertains to the total number of equivalent sites in terms of the distance between the defects rather than the distinguishable site symmetries.

* See references 1 and 12 for similar site symmetries in NaCl lattice.

TABLE I

Point Group Symmetries and Values of L_j , R_j and E_j^{vp} for $V_{Cl}-V'_{Cs}$ Pairs in $CsCl$.

j	Symmetry and Ion position	L_j	R_j (in a_0 units)	E_j^{vp} (eV)	j	Symmetry and Ion position	L_j	R_j (in a_0 units)	E_j^{vp} (eV)
1	$C_{3v} \left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	8	$\sqrt{3}/2$	0.636	14	$C_s \left(\frac{7}{2} \frac{7}{2} \frac{3}{2} \right)$	24	$\sqrt{107}/2$	0.106
2	$C_s \left(\frac{3}{2} \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	24	$\sqrt{11}/2$	0.332		$C_1 \left(\frac{9}{2} \frac{5}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	48		
3	$C_s \left(\frac{3}{2} \frac{3}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	24	$\sqrt{19}/2$	0.252	15	$C_1 \left(\frac{9}{2} \frac{5}{2} \frac{3}{2} \right)$	48	$\sqrt{115}/2$	0.102
4	$C_{3v} \left(\frac{3}{2} \frac{3}{2} \frac{3}{2} \right)$	8	$\sqrt{27}/2$	0.212	16	$C_1 \left(\frac{11}{2} \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	48	$\sqrt{123}/2$	0.099
	$C_s \left(\frac{5}{2} \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	24			17	$C_s \left(\frac{9}{2} \frac{5}{2} \frac{5}{2} \right)$	24	$\sqrt{131}/2$	0.096
5	$C_1 \left(\frac{5}{2} \frac{3}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	48	$\sqrt{35}/2$	0.186		$C_1 \left(\frac{11}{2} \frac{3}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	48		
6	$C_s \left(\frac{5}{2} \frac{3}{2} \frac{3}{2} \right)$	24	$\sqrt{43}/2$	0.168		$C_1 \left(\frac{9}{2} \frac{7}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	48		
7	$C_s \left(\frac{5}{2} \frac{5}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	24	$\sqrt{51}/2$	0.154	18	$C_s \left(\frac{11}{2} \frac{3}{2} \frac{3}{2} \right)$	24	$\sqrt{139}/2$	0.093
	$C_s \left(\frac{7}{2} \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	24				$C_1 \left(\frac{9}{2} \frac{7}{2} \frac{3}{2} \right)$	48		
8	$C_s \left(\frac{5}{2} \frac{5}{2} \frac{3}{2} \right)$	24	$\sqrt{59}/2$	0.143	19	$C_{3v} \left(\frac{7}{2} \frac{7}{2} \frac{7}{2} \right)$	8	$\sqrt{147}/2$	0.090
	$C_1 \left(\frac{7}{2} \frac{3}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	48				$C_1 \left(\frac{11}{2} \frac{5}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	48		
9	$C_s \left(\frac{7}{2} \frac{3}{2} \frac{3}{2} \right)$	24	$\sqrt{67}/2$	0.134	20	$C_1 \left(\frac{11}{2} \frac{5}{2} \frac{3}{2} \right)$	48	$\sqrt{155}/2$	0.088
10	$C_{3v} \left(\frac{5}{2} \frac{5}{2} \frac{5}{2} \right)$	8	$\sqrt{75}/2$	0.127		$C_1 \left(\frac{9}{2} \frac{7}{2} \frac{5}{2} \right)$	48		
	$C_1 \left(\frac{7}{2} \frac{5}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	48			21	$C_s \left(\frac{9}{2} \frac{9}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	24	$\sqrt{163}/2$	0.086
11	$C_1 \left(\frac{7}{2} \frac{5}{2} \frac{5}{2} \right)$	48	$\sqrt{83}/2$	0.120	22	$C_s \left(\frac{11}{2} \frac{5}{2} \frac{5}{2} \right)$	24	$\sqrt{171}/2$	0.084
	$C_s \left(\frac{9}{2} \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	24				$C_1 \left(\frac{9}{2} \frac{9}{2} \frac{3}{2} \right)$	48		
12	$C_1 \left(\frac{9}{2} \frac{3}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	48	$\sqrt{91}/2$	0.115		$C_1 \left(\frac{13}{2} \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	48		
13	$C_s \left(\frac{7}{2} \frac{5}{2} \frac{5}{2} \right)$	24	$\sqrt{99}/2$	0.110					
	$C_1 \left(\frac{9}{2} \frac{3}{2} \frac{3}{2} \right)$	48							

TABLE 1—(Contd.).

j	Symmetry and Ion position	L_j	R_j (in a_0 units)	E_j^{vp} (eV)	j	Symmetry and Ion position	L_j	R_j (in a_0 units)	E_j^{vp} (eV)
23	$C_s \left(\frac{9}{2} \frac{7}{2} \frac{7}{2} \right)$	24	$\sqrt{179}/2$	0.082	27	$C_s \left(\frac{9}{2} \frac{9}{2} \frac{7}{2} \right)$	24	$\sqrt{211}/2$	0.075
	$C_1 \left(\frac{11}{2} \frac{7}{2} \frac{3}{2} \right)$	48				$C_1 \left(\frac{11}{2} \frac{9}{2} \frac{3}{2} \right)$	48		
	$C_1 \left(\frac{13}{2} \frac{3}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	48			28	$C_1 \left(\frac{11}{2} \frac{7}{2} \frac{7}{2} \right)$	48	$\sqrt{219}/2$	0.074
24	$C_1 \left(\frac{13}{2} \frac{3}{2} \frac{3}{2} \right)$	48	$\sqrt{187}/2$	0.080		$C_1 \left(\frac{13}{2} \frac{5}{2} \frac{5}{2} \right)$	48		
25	$C_1 \left(\frac{13}{2} \frac{5}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	48	$\sqrt{195}/2$	0.078	29	$C_s \left(\frac{15}{2} \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	24	$\sqrt{227}/2$	0.073
	$C_1 \left(\frac{11}{2} \frac{7}{2} \frac{5}{2} \right)$	48				$C_1 \left(\frac{13}{2} \frac{7}{2} \frac{3}{2} \right)$	48		
26	$C_1 \left(\frac{13}{2} \frac{5}{2} \frac{3}{2} \right)$	48	$\sqrt{203}/2$	0.077		$C_1 \left(\frac{11}{2} \frac{9}{2} \frac{5}{2} \right)$	48		
	$C_1 \left(\frac{11}{2} \frac{9}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	48			30	$C_1 \left(\frac{15}{2} \frac{3}{2} \frac{1}{2} \right)$	48	$\sqrt{235}/2$	0.071

TABLE 2

Point Group Symmetries and Values of L_j , R_j and E_j^{iv} for $I \cdot C_s - V' C_s$ Pairs in $CsCl$

j	Symmetry and Ion Position	L_j	R_j (in σ_0 units)	E_j^{iv} (eV)
1	C_{4v} (100)	6	$\sqrt{1}$	0.550
2	C_{2v} (110)	12	$\sqrt{2}$	0.389
3	C_{3v} (111)	8	$\sqrt{3}$	0.318
4	C_{4v} (200)	6	$\sqrt{4}$	0.275
5	C_s (210)	24	$\sqrt{5}$	0.246
6	C_s (211)	24	$\sqrt{6}$	0.224
7	—	—	—	—
8	C_{2v} (220)	12	$\sqrt{8}$	0.194
9	C_{4v} (300)	6	$\sqrt{9}$	0.183
	C_s (221)	24		
10	C_s (310)	24	$\sqrt{10}$	0.174
11	C_s (311)	24	$\sqrt{11}$	0.166
12	C_{3v} (222)	8	$\sqrt{12}$	0.159

TABLE 2—(Contd)

j	Symmetry and Ion Position	L_j	R_j (in a_0 units)	$E_j^{1/2}$ (eV)
13	C_s (320)	24	$\sqrt{13}$	0.152
14	C_1 (321)	48	$\sqrt{14}$	0.147
15	—	—	—	—
16	C_{4v} (400)	6	$\sqrt{16}$	0.137
17	C_s (410)	24	$\sqrt{17}$	0.133
	C_s (322)	24		
18	C_{3v} (330)	12	$\sqrt{18}$	0.129
	C_s (411)	24		
19	C_s (311)	24	$\sqrt{19}$	0.126
20	C_s (420)	24	$\sqrt{20}$	0.123
21	C_1 (421)	48	$\sqrt{21}$	0.120
22	C_s (332)	24	$\sqrt{22}$	0.117
23	—	—	—	—
24	C_s (422)	24	$\sqrt{24}$	0.112
25	C_{4v} (500)	6	$\sqrt{25}$	0.110
	C_s (430)	24		
26	C_s (510)	24	$\sqrt{26}$	0.108
	C_1 (431)	48		
27	C_{3v} (333)	8	$\sqrt{27}$	0.106
	C_s (511)	24		
28	—	—	—	—
29	C_s (520)	24	$\sqrt{29}$	0.102
	C_1 (432)	48		
30	C_1 (521)	48	$\sqrt{30}$	0.100

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